

**CELL TRANSPLANTATION IN
CHRONIC MYELOID LEUKEMIA:
CURRENT STATUS AND FUTURE
DIRECTIONS**

Abstract

The acquisition of tyrosine kinase BCR-ABL1 in hematopoietic stem cells leads to the development of leukemic stem cells (LSCs), causing chronic myeloid leukemia (CML). While tyrosine kinase inhibitors (TKIs) effectively control CML, enabling treatment-free remission, CML LSCs, resistant to TKIs, persist during long-term therapy, impeding cure prospects and elevating relapse risk. Ongoing research is focused on exploring strategies for LSC eradication, highlighting survival mechanisms and potential gene mutations impacting clinical outcomes. This review outlines current preclinical approaches and upcoming challenges in the pursuit of a cure for CML, aiming to address the persistence of resistant LSCs and enhance long-term remission rates.

Keywords: BCR, ABL1, CML, TKIs, LSC

Introduction

Leukemia's early history spans 200 years, with Peter Cullen noting milky blood in splenitis acutus in 1811. Alfred Velpeau observed pus in blood arteries (1825), and Alfred Donne discovered halted white blood cell maturation (1844). John Bennett coined "leucocythemia" based on purulent leucocyte buildup (1845), while Rudolf Virchow described leukemia's white-and-red-blood cell imbalance in 1847. Henry Fuller made the first microscopic diagnosis in 1846 (Kampen, 2012). Leukemia has four main types and there are acute lymphocytic, chronic lymphocytic, acute myeloid, and chronic myeloid. It categorizes into acute or chronic based on speed and lymphoid or myelogenous based on cell origin. Acute lymphocytic leukemia, starting in bone marrow lymphoid cells, is the most common, affecting both adults and children, spreading rapidly to other body areas (Gluzman, D.F, et al., 2015).

Chronic myeloid leukemia (CML), a form of white blood cell cancer originating in bone marrow's myeloid cells, is marked by a chromosomal abnormality known as the Philadelphia chromosome, producing the BCR-ABL gene (Jepsen, M.S, A, et al., 2017). This gene triggers uncontrolled growth of leukemia cells, displacing healthy cells and causing insufficient blood cell levels. CML progresses slowly, often with gradual and asymptomatic onset. Diagnosing CML may stem from incidental discovery through unrelated blood tests, showcasing elevated

white blood cell counts. While symptoms may emerge over time, some patients remain asymptomatic at diagnosis, underscoring the insidious nature of this chronic leukemia (Etienne, G, et al., 2017).

Identify the biological basis of CML

Chronic Myelogenous Leukemia (CML) is a form of bone marrow malignancy affecting adults, characterized by a gradual increase in white blood cell counts. Also known as chronic granulocytic leukemia, CML can occur at any age. Unlike acute forms of leukemia, CML progresses slowly leukemia or chronic myeloid leukemia, it primarily impacts myelogenous cells. While rare in (Zhang, B, et al., 2010). The discovery of therapies for chronic myelogenous leukemia has significantly improved outlooks, providing relief and extending the lives of many affected individuals. Typically symptomless, the identification of the disease often involves a blood test. Additional indicators may include bone pain, easy bleeding, unexplained weight gain, fever, appetite loss, fatigue, weight loss despite exercise, and pain and stiffness under the left rib cage, along with excessive perspiration during sleep (Zhang, B, et al., 2012). When the gene is present in bone marrow units altered, chronic myelogenous leukemia can happen. Scientists have identified the mechanism's cause even if its origin is unknown. It may lead to chronic myelogenous leukemia (Zhang, B, et al., 2016). According to these research reports, imatinib mesylate induces remission in CML patients, but does not eliminate leukemia primary cells that have a tendency to relapse. In the initial investigation, treatment with HDAC inhibitor IM therapy could eliminate significant amounts of CML cells. Later investigations found more causal signs (Giustacchini, A, et al., 2017). subsequently identified MPL expression levels as a prognostic determinant of CML LTHSC heterologous leukemia initiation and drug sensitivity, suggesting that high MPL-expressing CML primary cells are potential targets for therapy (Kesarwani, M, et al., 2017).

In chronic myelogenous leukemia (CML), patients exhibit 9 extra-long and 22 small chromosomes, forming the Philadelphia chromosome (Ph chromosome), a fusion of chromosomes 9 and 22. This results in the BCR-ABL gene, producing an abnormal tyrosine

kinase that leads to uncontrolled growth of white blood cells. Despite efforts to counteract this with tyrosine kinase inhibitors, the strategy often proves ineffective. The BCR-ABL gene prevents proper development and aging of white blood cells, contributing to the characteristic features of CML. In 90% of cases, patients display the Philadelphia chromosome, highlighting its central role in the disease's pathology (Hughes, A, et al., 2017).

Figure 01: *Formation of BCR-ABL*

Treatments for the CML

Patients with chronic myeloid leukemia have common therapeutic options. Targeted therapy, chemotherapy, immunotherapy, donor lymphocyte infusion, and high-dose chemotherapy with stem cell implantation are commonly used. Clinical trials, testing new medicines, offer an additional avenue. While side effects are possible, patients may consider participating in a clinical study before, during, or after their cancer therapy, which may involve further testing.

Targeted therapy involves identifying and targeting specific cancer cells using therapeutic drugs or other chemicals. Tyrosine kinase inhibitors such as imatinib, mesylate, dasatinib, nilotinib, ponatinib, bosutinib and acciminib are used to treat CML. Although thought to be

less toxic than chemotherapy, it has been found that side effects can occur (Gómez-Almaguer, D., et al., 2016). Side effects of this treatment include high blood pressure, fatigue, mouth sores, nail changes, skin problems and liver related problems. As the advantages of this therapeutic method, it can be mentioned that the healthy cells are not affected, and the quick response is given because the attention is directed only to the target cells. On the downside, some patients may develop resistance to treatment over time, limiting long-term effectiveness (Holtz, M.S, et al., 2002). These treatments are expensive and cause financial problems for some patients. European countries such as Sweden, which are developed countries, have shown the effectiveness of this treatment. But due to lack of resources and financial problems in developing countries, access has been limited (Baccarani, M., et al., 2015).

Chemotherapy is a treatment that stops cancer from spreading throughout the body when a drug is injected into a muscle or vein. These treatments use powerful drugs to kill rapidly dividing cancer cells. Cancer shrinkage and symptom relief can be seen as benefits of prolonging life. By this method, not only cancer cells but also healthy cells are destroyed, and the occurrence of side effects is disadvantageous (Anon., 1994). Treatment with TKIs combined and with primary stem cell transplantation has been able to reduce annual mortality.

Immunotherapy stimulates the immune system as a cancer treatment. Fortified by substances produced in the body naturally or by laboratory methods. Interferon affects cancer cell division and slows growth. Early detection of cancer can reduce side effects. But the level of achievement is low (Andrea Erika Held, et al., 2013). A significant component of CML therapy in the United States are options such as targeted and lymphocyte infusions.

Donor lymphocyte infusion is a treatment performed after stem cell transplantation. A subset of the donor's lymphocytes and white blood cells can be frozen for later use. DLI is proven to be effective in treating relapsed CML after cell transplantation. But while the management of relapsed CML patients is challenging and DLI is an attractive option, its efficacy should be considered with caution. Countries such as the US and Japan use this therapy to a significant extent to manage CML relapse after cell transplantation (Abraham, S.A, et al., 2016).

Chronic Myeloid Leukemia (CML) treatment has evolved, with tyrosine kinase inhibitors (TKIs) now being the primary approach, reducing the need for stem cell transplantation (SCT). However, for younger patients, especially those without positive responses to TKIs or in advanced disease stages, SCT remains a potential cure. Compatibility with a donor, like a

sibling, enhances eligibility (Arora, A. & Scholar, E.M., , 2005). High-dose chemotherapy or low radiation aims to eliminate leukemia cells but can harm healthy bone marrow cells. Post-treatment, blood-forming stem cells are transplanted via either peripheral blood stem cell transplant (PBSCT) or bone marrow transplant (BMT). PBSCT has largely replaced BMT in contemporary practice (Ye, W., Wu, X., Wang, X., et al., 2022). Transplants are crucial for those nearing or diagnosed in rapid or blast phases. The shift to TKIs as the primary treatment underscores the diminishing role of SCT in managing CML.

Allogeneic and autologous stem cell transplantation are the two main types. In autologous transplants, a patient's own stem cells are extracted and used, but leukemia cells may be present in the collection. Allogeneic transplants use stem cells from a donor, typically a close family member, with matching tissue types to minimize complications. For treating Chronic Myeloid Leukemia (CML), allogeneic transplants are common due to the risk of obtaining leukemia cells along with the patient's stem cells. However, this procedure carries serious potential side effects, making it less suitable for older or sicker patients (Prost, S, et al., 2015).

Stem cell transplants, often employed after intense chemotherapy and possibly radiation therapy, aim to restore the body's ability to generate new blood cells. In leukemia cases, the transplant may directly combat malignancy through graft-versus-tumor or graft-versus-leukemia phenomena. White blood cells from the donor attack any remaining cancer cells in the recipient's body, enhancing the transplant's success (Welniak, L.A., et al., 2007). The transplant involves obtaining healthy blood-forming stem cells from the bloodstream, bone marrow, or umbilical cord. These stem cells enter the bloodstream and migrate to the bone marrow, aiding in the recovery of therapy-induced cell loss. Mini transplants, a type of allogeneic transplant, use less cancer treatment than traditional transplants. Although they destroy some cancer cells, they preserve some blood-forming stem cells. This allogeneic transplant variant lowers the immune system to prevent rejection of donor stem cells (Scott, M.T, et al., 2016).

However, one kind of autologous transplant is a tandem transplant. In a tandem transplant, they have both a stem cell transplant and an intensive round of chemotherapy. Then another round of intensive chemotherapy and a second stem cell transplant a few weeks or months later. Numerous criteria determine which kind of stem cell transplant is appropriate and whether it is possible (Thomas Sr, 1994). The kind of cancer patient have the degree of progression of patient's disease, ability to use own stem cells, the availability of donor stem cells that match

patient, the possibility of additional cancer treatments, ability to withstand large doses of chemotherapy, and the existence of any other significant health issues previous treatments you've received patient's physician will carefully consider these worries in light of the advantages and disadvantages of each kind of stem cell transplant and go over them with patient (Gratwohl, A, et al., 2002).

The donor's stem cells will be examined for their HLAs (human leukocyte antigens) in order to determine if are a match. The majority of the cells in body have sets of proteins called HLAs, which act as markers. Every individual possesses a unique set of HLAs. The likelihood that body will accept the donor's stem cells is higher the more HLAs patient's and the donor share. A brother or sister is typically the ideal candidate for an allogeneic stem cell transplant. Prior to receiving a stem cell transplant, high dosages of cancer treatment may raise patient's risk of infection, induce bleeding, and leave feeling depleted and worn out. Both immediate and long-term complications may result from stem cell transplants (Suttorp, M. & Millot, F., , 2010). As temporary issues, weariness, loss of appetite, nausea, and vomiting, skin rashes, hair loss, mouth sores, and transplanting stem cells and As persistent issues with infertility, Cataracts, which cause clouding of the lens of the eye and impair vision, and newly discovered secondary cancer harm to the liver, kidneys, lungs, or heart weakening of the bones and muscles Discuss any potential side effects you may experience, their potential severity, and what to do about them with doctor or nurse. If experience difficulty eating after receiving a stem cell transplant, speaking with a dietician may be beneficial.

GVHD, or graft-versus-host disease

After an allogeneic transplant, graft-versus-host disease (GVHD) can occur when donor white blood cells attack the recipient's cells, leading to potential harm to organs like the skin, liver, and intestines. GVHD can manifest as acute within the first three months post-transplant or chronic three months later. Both forms pose serious risks.

Stem cell transplantation is a complex and costly procedure requiring extended hospital stays and specialized care. Following the transplant, patients typically have a 100-day window to return home if all goes well, necessitating constant supervision from an experienced physician. The process involves high-dose chemotherapy or radiation therapy, followed by a recovery

period (Jamil, M.O. & Mineishi, S., 2015). Stem cells are infused on day zero, and the healing process begins, with frequent blood count monitoring. Full immune system recovery varies, taking months to years. The impact on individuals differs based on transplant type, prior treatment, cancer stage, and overall health. Predicting post-transplant feelings is challenging, and the ability to resume work may be affected (Copelan, 2006). The procedure, from high-dose treatments to recovery, spans months, with frequent hospital visits. Staying close to the hospital is often essential during this period due to potential exhaustion and follow-up appointments.

Future directions of the stem cell transplantation

Continued research focuses on enhancing primary cell transplantation outcomes for chronic myeloid leukemia (CML). Refinements in primary cell engraftment protocols consider patient characteristics and disease stage. Ongoing investigations explore combination therapies like stem cell transplantation (SCT) with targeted drugs such as TKIs to boost efficacy and reduce relapse rates. Creative strategies address complications post-SCT, tailoring therapies as needed. CML's impact on long-term hematopoietic stem cells (LTHSCs) involves reduced homing and retention in bone marrow, linked to altered cytokine expression (Cortes, J & Lang, F, 2021). Understanding the heterogeneity of leukemic LTHSCs remains a challenge. High MPL expression in LTHSCs is associated with enhanced JAK/STAT signaling and increased leukemogenic capacity. Inhibiting MPL expression in CML LTHSCs reduces JAK/STAT signaling and leukemogenic potential. Ongoing inspections aim to address existing weaknesses, ultimately improving the safety and effectiveness of stem cell transplantation for CML (Gratwohl, et al., 2006).

Identifying specific patient populations most likely to benefit from stem cell transplantation, reducing transplant-related complications, exploring alternative stem cell sources such as umbilical cord blood to expand donor options and reduce the risk of graft-versus-host disease (GVHD) may lead to more fruitful solutions in the future (Clarkson, B, et al., 2003). Tests will be done to find out. Investigating the use of new agents or combination therapies with transplantation to improve treatment efficacy, studying immunological approaches such as chimeric antigen receptor (CAR) T-cell therapy combined with stem cell transplantation,

Researching ways to improve graft-versus-leukemia (GVL) effects while reducing GVHD risks, exploring techniques such as T-cell depletion or adding specific cell subsets to enhance the anti-leukemic activity of the graft, Investigating the use of low doses of TKIs or other targeted therapies post-transplant to maintain remission, using genetic profiling and other personalized medicine approaches to tailor treatment strategies based on individual patient characteristics, There is a strong focus on investigating the use of gene editing technology to improve the safety and effectiveness of stem cell transplants, and the trials that have been conducted so far are encouraging that each of these issues may be addressed in the future (Osman, A.E. & Deininger, M.W., 2021).

Conclusion

For patients with chronic myeloid leukemia (CML), stem cell transplantation (SCT) has the potential to improve prognosis. Its effectiveness is highlighted by recent investigations. Randomized trials have shown that SCT improves overall survival in CML. Stem cell transplantation, a curative mechanism for CML, is done along with chemotherapy. It is said to be an efficient way to control the variables and reactions that affect the results. Stem cell transplantation specifically, allogeneic stem cell transplantation appears to be a viable and successful treatment for chronic myeloid leukemia, offering increased chances of survival as well as future cures. However, treatment methods vary according to the patient's age, health level, and CML condition. Finally, at present, stem cell transplantation is a treatment method that gives very successful results for CML.

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